

Investigation of the Thermal and Surface Properties of Glass-Carbon Hybrid Fiber Epoxy Composite

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Abstract: The modern world has seen a rapid surge in the usage of composite materials in recent times for their widespread applications and versatility. This study investigated thermal properties and the surface morphology of carbon and glass fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composite fabricated by vacuum infusion molding (VIM) process. Lee's and Charlton's method for thermal conductivity of bad conductors proved its poor thermal conductivity, where the value was found $0.52 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. Coefficient of thermal expansion was measured by Thermomechanical analysis (TMA), which also revealed that the thermal expansion occurred in multiple stages and subsequently resulting in multiple coefficient of thermal expansion. The thermogravimetric analysis disclosed the degradation rate, glass transition temperature, onset temperature, degradation steps, and their possible causes. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to characterize its surface properties which showed the composite's internal structure. All of the tests displayed promising results in terms of its potential in high-temperature applications, such as in the aerospace industry.

Keywords: hybrid composites; morphology; thermal conductivity; thermomechanical analysis; vacuum infusion molding

1. Introduction

The engineering world has seen a rapid surge in innovation of modern materials, in pursuit of superior quality, usability, and versatility. Composite materials have become a familiar name in the domain of manufacturing industries in the past few decades, because of their corrosion resistance, permanence, availability, and cheap cost¹⁻². Composites consist of two or more distinct materials and if combined, they display properties that are greater than the sum of their parts separately^{3,5}. Composites consist of two phases, the stiffer component which is generally found in an elongated shape, stays with the softer part that is called The Matrix^{6,8}. The matrix phase has multiple functions, it holds the shape of the composite, ensures the stability of the composite when mechanical or thermal stress is applied, provides outdoor resistance, and it separates the fibers from one another so that they can maintain their originality⁹⁻¹⁰. Various matrices are

available with their specialty. Polyesters and vinyl esters complement glass fiber because it is cheaper; thermosetting polyimides, bismaleimide (BMI), and cyanate esters are used in high-temperature applications, while epoxy resins are used for structural, military, or aerospace components¹¹⁻¹⁴. Apart from these polymeric matrices, mineral matrices, and metallic matrices are also available¹⁵. The other part is known as the reinforcement, which could be particles or fibers in the form of roving, strand, or woven¹⁶⁻¹⁸. The reinforcement is the primary component that bears the load applied to the material and thus generally is stronger than the matrix¹⁹. Composite materials can be found in many industries, ranging from medical to automotive applications, due to them being lightweight and corrosion-resistant, which is exactly why their demand is increasing rapidly every other day²⁰⁻²¹. There are several factors on which the properties

of composites might depend. In an investigation of the effect of different filler materials on composites reinforced with glass, carbon, and Kevlar fibers it was found that the ceramic fillers (alumina and silicon carbide) have a significant effect on the physical properties of the composites²²). Fillers like Graphene or Carbon Nanotube (CNT) impacts important factors like Young's modulus and toughness, as well as enhancing their thermal stability²³). These fillers can be used together in composites to achieve higher standards, but that leaves it in a complex situation because it depends heavily on orientation and fabrication technique. Thermal conductivity and diffusivity have an inversely proportional relation with fiber loading²⁴). Fiber length affects the thermal properties of composites, an increase in fiber length can help achieve thermal stability²⁵). Other than the materials, the interfacial bonding between the matrix and the reinforcement can significantly impact the quality²⁶). Chemical treatment can assist in decreasing the wear rate and friction coefficient of different kinds of composites²⁷).

The core materials, carbon, and glass fiber are known all over the world for their advanced applications. Glass fibers, being relatively cheaper than carbon fibers, used for manufacturing home appliances since ancient times²⁸). Their usage spreads across modern dental appliances²⁹⁻³⁰), structural composites³¹⁻³²), as well as marine and piping industries³³). Different types of glass fibers are available at the market, to be chosen according to the required properties, shown in Table 1³⁴). On the other hand, Carbon fibers could be a suitable material for upcoming aerospace applications such as rocket nozzles³⁵⁻³⁶) and are predicted to take over half of the overall mass of an aircraft³⁷). Carbon fiber based composites are considered to be the future of high speed applications, both in the automobile and aerospace industry³⁸). They can be used as the anode in Lithium-ion, Lithium-sulfur, and Sodium-ion batteries, and can also be hybridized with other components to enhance the cyclability of Lithium-ion batteries³⁹). CFRP (Carbon fiber reinforced plastics) composites are well respected in dental, aerospace, textile, and biomedical applications^{40,42}). The hybrid composite of carbon and glass fiber showed better stability than their composites both in Differential Scanning Calorimetry and Thermogravimetric Analysis; the flexural strength of the hybrid composite was a cut above the rest, but Carbon fiber composites showed better tensile strength and yield strength than both hybrid and glass fiber reinforced composites and the transverse strength were found nearly same for both hybrid and carbon fiber composite⁴³). In another study, hybrid carbon and glass fiber-based (CGFRP) composites for structural applications were found to be superior in mechanical properties to fully carbon fiber or glass fiber-based composites⁴⁴). It was revealed that the failure strain of hybrid carbon and glass

fiber-based composites was higher than that of carbon fiber-reinforced composites⁴⁵). An interesting investigation compared the properties of carbon and glass fiber-based laminates and concluded that carbon fiber laminates are better than glass fiber laminates in cases where loading was reinforcement-based, such as the tensile loading, and glass fibers performed better where loading was matrix-based, such as compressive loading⁴⁶). An experiment was carried out to find the possibilities of using HFRP (Hybrid fiber-reinforced plastic) composites for aeronautic applications, and the decision was made that carbon and glass fiber-reinforced composites possess better thermal properties than carbon-fiber-reinforced and glass fiber-reinforced composites, although the mechanical properties of carbon fiber-reinforced composites came out greater than the HFRP composites⁴⁷). Flexural strength was found to be better for carbon and glass fiber-based HFRP composites compared to their individual composites⁴⁸). Also, for both carbon and glass fiber, it was found that the addition of these components in FRP (Fiber-reinforced plastic) composites has a positive impact on the mechanical and thermal properties⁴⁹).

Table 1: Types of Glass fibers

Glass Type	Application
E	For electrical appliances.
E-Cr	For corrosion resistance applications.
S	For high mechanical strength.
R	For high strength which is in the middle of E and S.

Engineering materials possess several properties upon which their applications depend, mechanical properties, chemical properties, and thermal properties are some examples. For instance, a material possessing excellent thermal stability could be used for high-temperature applications, usage of chemically active materials should be utilized on appropriate conditions, where their activeness or inertness can instigate or jeopardize the agenda. Thermal investigations can be carried out in several ways, one popular method is Thermogravimetric analysis or TGA, where the change in mass of a component or compound is measured with controlled increasing temperature and can be used to measure several physio-chemical properties⁵⁰⁻⁵¹). The loss of mass might be the result of moisture evaporation, and mass loss in elevated temperature is credited to material decomposition⁵²). Another approach is Differential Thermal Analysis or DTA, where the change of phase of the substance is observed upon constant heating and subsequent comparison with a reference material⁵³). Differential Thermogravimetric Analysis, or DTA is a technique for

measuring the weight difference of a material after heating in elevated temperature⁵⁴). TMA, or Thermomechanical analysis, commonly used for polymers, or polymer matrix composites, is an appropriate method of detecting precise changes in the dimension of the material under special conditions⁵⁵⁻⁵⁶, glass transition temperature was measured using this method, which is the temperature when a polymer transforms from a glassy state to the elastic state⁵⁷). Thermal conductivity can be measured in many ways, one of the most inexpensive, versatile, and easy-to-use ways is the Lee's and Charlton method, where heat is flown through the internal body, following certain easy steps, and basic calculation, thermal conductivity can be easily measured⁵⁸). To better understand any material's crystalline structure, chemical composition, and micrometer (μm) level analysis, Scanning Electron Microscopy is a popular choice that utilizes a high-energy electron beam to take pictures of the microstructure that is not visible to the human eyes^{59,61}). The two materials, glass, and carbon fiber, both are recognized for their applications, and a good number of scientific investigations have been conducted in the past, but not much has been discussed in terms of the thermal properties of these two materials combined as hybrid composites.

This study explicates the thermal stability and surface quality of carbon and glass fiber-reinforced composites with the intention of investigating its prospect in different industries where the material could be exposed to high temperatures for a long period of time, such as the aerospace industry. This study aims to determine its thermal properties by measuring its thermal degradation rate, which will prove its stability against heat exposure, and thermal conductivity, which will corroborate its thermal insulation nature, and morphological analysis, which will display its microstructure.

2. Methodology

2.1. Materials

In this study, TC-06-P Woven Carbon Fiber, and Biaxial LT Glass Fiber, E-BX600 were used as reinforcement, and are supplied by RP Products Sdn Bhd, Bandar Baru Seri Alam, Malaysia. The properties of the fibers are displayed in Table 2. The reason behind choosing these two fibers is their strength-to-weight ratio being supreme, excellent thermal insulation, and ease of processing. EPOLAM 2040 epoxy along with EPOLAM 2042 resin hardener was used as the matrix in this experiment. The prime reason behind choosing epoxy was due to its low viscosity that allows better fiber impregnation. The physical properties of the resin and hardener can be found in Table 3.

Table 2: Properties of the fibers used in this experiment

Properties	Fibers	
	Glass fiber	Carbon fiber
Area Weight (g/m^2)	301	197
Density(g/cm^3)	2.54	1.80
Thickness (mm)	0.31	0.16
Tensile Strength (ksi)	360	512
Tensile Modulus (msi)	11.4	33.4
Strain to Failure (%)	3.0	1.5

Table 3: Properties of epoxy and hardener used in this experiment

Properties	EPOLAM 2040 epoxy	EPOLAM 2042 hardener
Tensile strength	75 MPa	75 MPa
Flexural strength	124 MPa	125 MPa
Temperature Resistance	85°C	93°C
Mix viscosity at 25°C	1300 centipoise	280 centipoise
Density at 25°C	1.16 g/cm^3	0.95 g/cm^3

2.2. Fabrication of the composites

Vacuum Infusion Molding (VIM) was chosen as the fabrication technique for this study, whereas a total of 9 layers of fibers were stacked together, lamina stacking sequence is displayed in Figure 1. The fiber orientation was kept at 0/90°C throughout the process. There are a total of 9 layers of fibers, the sequence being (C-G-G-G-C-G-G-G-C), where carbon and Glass fiber are denoted by C and G respectively. At the very beginning, a thinner scraper was used to clean the glass mold. As mold mold-releasing agent, Wax was applied for quick removal of the finished product from the mold. The sealant tape was applied to the mold which was around 50 mm bigger than the actual laminate size. Then, the fiber clothes were embedded in the mold within the sealant tape area. Afterward, polymer mesh and peel ply were also applied. To regulate the flow of resin, a spiral tube was used with the help of sealant tape. A connection was given between the inlet to the resin and the outlet to the vacuum chamber. In the end, using sealant tape, the mold was sealed properly so that there were no leakages. To further ensure it, the vacuum pump was turned on at 80 KPa vacuum pressure and kept still for observation for 20 minutes. After absolute sealing was ensured, the resin was allowed to flow inside the mold by opening the clamp in the inlet pipe, which was then closed after impregnation was completed. The fabrication process is demonstrated in Figure 2. It was kept overnight for 12 hours to solidify. Finally, at the end of the process, the composite was kept in the oven at 80°C for around 6 hours for even better curing.

Fig. 1: Lamina stacking sequence.

2.3. Thermal Properties

2.3.1. Thermal conductivity

Lee's and Charlton's method for determining the thermal conductivity of bad conductors was used to evaluate the thermal conductivity of fabricated composites since polymer-based composites are known to be insulators or

Fig 2: The Vacuum Infusion Molding setup for this study

very bad conductors of heat. A thin circular disc of 10 cm diameter was taken as the specimen ⁶²). Huber Thermostat Waterbath Polystat CC1 machine, as shown in Figure 3, was used and a basic K-type thermocouple was used to measure the temperature. The thickness of the specimen was 0.39 cm. The Huber Thermostat Waterbath Polystat CC1 machine was used to heat the steam chamber. At first, 60°C temperature was given as input in the machine, which it reached quite quickly. Since it was in direct contact with the specimen and

Fig. 3: Experimental setup of Lee's and Charlton's disc method

the specimen subsequently touched Lee's Copper disc, the heat generated in the steam chamber conducted into the specimen and Lee's disc as well. After the machine reached the desired 60°C, the thermocouple was inserted into the two holes of the steam chamber and Lee's disc to observe the steady state temperature while keeping the temperature at 60°C constant. At the steam chamber, the steady-state temperature, θ_1 was observed at 46°C, while the steady-state temperature at the upper disc, θ_2 was observed at 40°C. The next stage was to raise θ_2 10°C higher, at 50°C, also by taking the specimen out of the setup. The machine was turned off after it reached there and the specimen was reinserted in the middle. The final work was to let it cool down and to observe the temperature from 10°C higher than θ_2 , that is 50°C, to 10°C lower than θ_2 , which is 30°C. The entire reading observation took 84 minutes to complete, readings were taken every 30 seconds, and a temperature vs time graph was plotted, to find out the rate of cooling. The experiment was carried out with appropriate safety precautions, uniform room temperature, and under expert guidance. The diameter and mass of the disc were measured with a slide caliper and a digital weight machine respectively.

2.3.2. Thermomechanical Analysis

The thermomechanical analysis was carried out with TMA/SS EXSTAR 6300, SII Nanotechnology, Japan, controlled by an EXSTAR 6300 controller. This test was conducted by heating the carbon and glass fiber reinforced composite first at 10°C/min under static load, ranging the temperature from 30°C to 120°C, and secondly, from 30°C to just above 200°C. Both tests were carried out under a nitrogen gas environment. The specimen was kept on the sample holder inside the apparatus. The TMA apparatus is equipped with a sensitive probe which stays embedded on the surface of the material. As temperature increases, the probe recognises the difference in dimension and records the data.

2.3.3. Thermogravimetric Analysis

The thermogravimetric analysis was carried out with a

TG/DTA 6300 system connected to an EXSTAR 6000 Station, Seiko Instrument Inc., Japan. An 8×8 mm specimen was prepared, and the test was conducted under a nitrogen

atmosphere, where the reference material was alumina. The heating rate was 20°C/min and the range of temperature was 30°C to 600°C.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Thermal Conductivity

The formula for measuring the thermal conductivity of a bad conductor using Lee's and Charlton's method is ⁶²⁾,

$$\text{Thermal conductivity, } K = \frac{Msd}{\alpha(\theta_1 - \theta_2)} \times \frac{d\theta}{dt}$$

Where,

Temperature of the lower disc, $\theta_1 = 46^\circ\text{C}$

Temperature of the upper disc, $\theta_2 = 40^\circ\text{C}$

Mass of the metal disc, $M = 0.782 \text{ kg}$,

Specific heat of copper (Lee's disc), $S = 0.384 \text{ kJ kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ ⁶³⁾,

Diameter of the specimen, $D = 10.01 \text{ cm}$, or 0.1001 m ,

The radius of the specimen, $r = \frac{D}{2} = 0.05005 \text{ m}$,

$$\text{Area of the specimen, } \alpha = \pi r^2 = 0.00787 \text{ m}^2$$

The thickness of the specimen, $d = 0.0039 \text{ m}$

From the tangent of the cooling curve in Figure 4, the Rate of cooling, $\frac{d\theta}{dt} = \frac{\text{Height of ordinate}}{\text{Height of abscissa}} = 0.0021 \text{ }^\circ\text{C/sec}$

Putting all the values in the formula, the thermal conductivity was found to be $0.52 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$, which is a very small value compared to metals. This depicts the amount of heat transferring from high temperature zone to the low temperature zone, proving the fact that polymeric composites are bad conductors which means means good insulators of heat and can be used in high-temperature applications.

3.2. Thermomechanical Analysis (TMA)

The thermomechanical analysis observed the change in dimensions of HFRP composite with increasing temperature. For the first test. the glass transition temperature was observed at 47.0 °C, the result can be seen in Figure 5. But the maximum contraction occurs at 73.5°C. On the other hand, the glass transition temperature for the second test was found at 63.9 °C, the result can be seen in Figure 6. Also, the maximum contraction was observed at 79.7 °C. In this experiment, the thermal expansion took place in three and five stages for test 1 and 2 respectively, the values of the coefficient of thermal expansion can be found in Table 4. The values were low in comparison with ceramics and metals, changing between negative and positive values, which is pretty common for composites. The reason behind it is that it is not a natural product, but rather made by human beings in laboratories, and not always the fabrication process goes

perfectly. The negative value defines that there has been a contraction instead of expansion and the positive value insinuates that there has been an expansion. It can be seen that there is contraction when the temperature stays between around 30°C and 90°C, whereas there is an expansion when the temperature increases. In the second test, the temperature was further elevated and another level of contraction was observed. It shows a trend of contraction with increasing temperature, then a slight expansion, followed by another contraction with further increase in temperature. Also, the values were rather low, which is a characteristic of thermoset-based polymeric materials because their chemical bond is mostly covalent, and epoxy, which is a thermoset, has been used here.

Fig. 4: Temperature vs Time curve for Glass and carbon fiber reinforced composite.

Fig. 5: Thermomechanical thermogram of the first test

Fig. 6: Thermomechanical thermogram of the second test

3.3. Thermogravimetric Analysis, Differential Thermal Analysis, and Differential Thermogravimetric Analysis (TG, DTA, DTG)

As mentioned, The TG, DTA, and DTG tests were carried out to investigate various thermal attributes of the fabricated material. Unlike metals, whose degradations are electrochemical, polymeric degradations are physiochemical. The chemical behavior of polymer is complex, hence not always the mechanism of degradation is well explained and understood⁶⁴. The thermogravimetric analysis gave a clear idea regarding the behavior of the decomposition. Figure 7 shows the Thermogravimetric (TG) curve for the fabricated composite of this research. At the beginning, the horizontal plane indicates no noteworthy loss

is present there. The TG curve shows an initial loss of 0.2% because of moisture content. The major degradation can be seen taking place in one step, which starts at 298.4 °C, with mass loss being 2%. Afterward, a rapid decomposition can be seen until 374.7°C with 16.4% mass loss. Furthermore, the decomposition of the sample started to decrease until it became stable at 501.5°C, above that the decomposition was constant till the end where the final mass loss was found to be 31.8%. It took around 355°C to loss 10% mass, 382°C to loss 20% mass, and 450°C for 30% mass loss. The DTA curve can be seen in Figure 8, which shows three endothermic peaks at 161.9°C, 380.6°C, and 441.7°C, denoted by points A, B, and C respectively. The glass point temperature was found at 370.1°C. Which actually means the energy required for the atoms to transform from one state to another, which will make them brittle¹⁴. The first two peaks may correspond to the removal of moisture content and melting of the substance, while the final peak might be the result of the major degradation or destruction of the polymeric material. The DTG curve, shown in Figure 9, exhibits one exothermic peak, which states that the maximum degradation occurred at 370.8°C, also known as “Peak degradation temperature”, and the rate of degradation was 4.41 mg/min or 4414 µg/min. It also shows that the onset temperature is 323.81°C and the offset temperature is 457.05°C. The onset and offset temperature are the points where degradation begins and finishes, respectively

Table 4: Values of coefficient of thermal expansion

Test	Stage	Temperature Range (°C)	Co-efficient of thermal expansion (°C ⁻¹)
First test	1	30.2 -41.6	-4.814×10 ⁻⁵
	2	41.2 -75.5	-1.031×10 ⁻³
	3	75.7°C-121.7	2.601×10 ⁻⁴
Second Test	1	31.9-49.5	2.25×10 ⁻⁵
	2	49.2-60.4	-1.26×10 ⁻⁴
	3	60.2-85.9	-7.49×10 ⁻⁴
	4	85.9-181.1	1.79×10 ⁻⁴
	5	180.9-208.7	-5.39×10 ⁻⁵

Fig. 7: TG curve for carbon and glass fiber reinforced composite

Fig. 8: DTA curve for carbon and glass fiber reinforced composite

Fig. 9: DTG curve for carbon and glass fiber reinforced composite

3.4 Morphological analysis

Here, Morphological study was done to understand microscopic details better, to find out the quality of the fabrication process, and to examine the properties including the defects and the relation of the constituents. The fiber-matrix interfacial adhesion is one of the primary elements affecting the mechanical characteristics of fiber-reinforced materials; a weak interfacial area will decrease the efficiency of stress transmission from the matrix to the reinforcement component, and low strength may be predicted⁶⁵⁻⁶⁶. Therefore, adding a filler to a polymer matrix composite may not always improve the material's qualities. The nature of the fiber and polymer components, the fiber aspect ratio, the processing method, and the treatment of the polymer or fiber are some of the elements that affect the quality of interfacial bonding⁶⁷⁻⁶⁹. SEM scans were a useful tool for illustrating the beneficial effects of carbon and glass fiber on polymer and composite specimens. SEM micrographs of the neat resin and associated carbon and glass fibers at various magnifications are shown in **Figure 10** below.

At the lower magnification level (at 100X) the layer of the carbon and glass fiber-reinforced composite can be seen. The bond of these fillers incorporated with resin is visible in the image. A gap between the matrix and the fiber is visible in this picture, the gap corresponds to poor interfacial adhesion, wettability, or insufficient matrix-reinforcement bonding during the fabrication⁷⁰⁻⁷¹. Voids, cracks, fiber tear, and fiber pull-out were also observed at this stage, which might occur because of the randomness of the fibers⁷², these defects and failures can impact the mechanical properties of the specimen⁷³. Higher magnification (at 200X) illustrates the synergism of the fillers together and remnants of glass and carbon fibers during the VIM process can be seen as well as some microvoids being more visible. In (at 1500X) Magnification the microphotographs clearly show some microcracking and microvoids on the surface of the specimens.. Resin binders along with fillers in the composite show nano fractures however they do create broader fracture regions by developing rougher surfaces, which allows them to halt the spread of cracks. This has the effect of effectively dissipating the fracture energy.

Fig. 10: SEM analysis of carbon and glass fiber reinforced composites a) 100X magnification b) 200X magnification c) 1500X magnification

4. Conclusion

The purpose of the presented work is to focus on the important and inherent thermal and surface properties of carbon and glass fiber-reinforced composite. The study proved the fact that glass fiber and carbon fiber can be combined as a composite for different industrial applications. The fabrication of the HFRP composite was carried out by vacuum infusion molding (VIM) process. The thermal conductivity test by Lee and Charlton's method corroborated the statement of polymers being poor thermal

conductors, where the value was found only $0.52 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. The thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), differential thermal analysis (DTA), and differential thermogravimetric analysis (DTA) gave valuable insights into the thermal properties of the composite, values like glass transition temperature, degradation rate and onset temperature were measured by these tests, the values being 370.1°C , 4.41 mg/min , and 339.0°C respectively. The DTA curve showed the stages of degradation and the probable reasons were also discussed. The thermomechanical analysis (TMA) revealed the coefficient of thermal expansion and the fact that the material has multiple coefficients of thermal expansion values. The

SEM analysis of HFRP specimens illustrates their internal structures and the synergism of carbon and glass fibers with resin binders. The micrographs show layer sequences of composites as well as internal fractures and voids that could significantly impact the properties of the composite. The relatively lower amount of voids and cracks justify the selection of the fabrication process. Following the study, carbon fibers offer important qualities when combined with glass fiber. This serves as a point of reference for choosing carbon and glass fibers as the potentially effective reinforcing material in FRP (Fiber Reinforced Plastic) composites. Additional studies combining carbon and glass along with fillers and microfibers may widen the scientific doorway for the creation of sophisticated multifunctional composites with a wider range of technological applications, prominently in the automobile or aerospace sector.

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Nomenclature

HFRP	Hybrid fiber-reinforced plastic
CFRP	Carbon fiber-reinforced plastic
TMA	Thermomechanical analysis
TG	Thermogravimetric analysis
DTG	Differential thermogravimetric analysis
DTA	Differential thermal analysis
SEM	Scanning electron microscopy

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